

IMPACT OF DENTAL PROSTHESES ON OCCLUSAL FUNCTION IN EDENTULOUS PATIENTS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META-ANALYSIS OF RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIALS

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ABSTRACT

Dental prostheses can improve oral health and have an impact on occlusal function in edentulous patients. For instance, implant-supported dentures are thought to improve masticatory efficiency and biting power; these more modern instruments have demonstrated to offer greater patient satisfaction than traditional complete dentures. Patient-related characteristics such as age, sex, and associated illnesses or comorbid conditions may influence treatment success. Even though total tooth loss is declining globally, edentulism is still frequent, especially in older persons. Modern prosthetics have a major positive impact on oral health overall and occlusal function. Enhancing patient well-being and optimizing treatment outcomes require an understanding of and attention to patient-specific requirements.

Keywords: Occlusal functioning, complete denture, lingualized accusation, quality of life.

INTRODUCTION

Dental Prostheses are artificial devices like dentures or dental implants that recreate missing teeth. Occlusal Function means the effectiveness of the bite, including chewing and speaking abilities after dental prostheses and edentulous patients are individuals without any natural teeth.

Edentulism a _debilitating irreversible condition if patient permanently loses one or more of their natural teeth. Edentulism is referred to as the "final marker of disease burden for oral health" [1]. Despite

a decline in the prevalence of complete tooth loss over the past decade, edentulism is still a global health issue that affects most commonly older adults [2].

According to WHO, oral diseases are prevalent noncommunicable diseases, affecting 45% of the worldwide population, and approximately 3.5 billion people in the entire globe are affected. The World Health Organization’s Global Oral Health Status Report (GOHSR) presented a comprehensive analysis of oral disease burden as it reported, according to data from 2022, almost 390 billion dollars are annually spent on oral health globally, this spending is variably distributed among countries. Global oral health report highlights severe inequalities with vulnerable and disadvantaged populations bearing the highest disease burden [3]. According to the CDC’s National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, which was conducted between 2011 and 2012 in the United States, 19% of adults aged 65 and over were edentulous. The prevalence was twice as high among those aged 75 and over (26%) compared to those aged 65–74 (13%) [4].

Occlusal Function is the tooth interaction while biting, chewing, and speaking and it is a linchpin of oral health, impacting mastication efficiency and speech clarity allowing people feel comfortable with optimal oral functioning. Occlusal Function is very complex interaction, it ensures the effective breakdown of food and proper alignment and spacing of teeth, thereby affecting phonetics. In case, when occlusal balance is disrupted, it can lead to various dental issues, including temporomandibular joint disorders and periodontal disease, which ultimately diminish the quality of life [5].

Dental prostheses come out as the strategic intervention measures and dental treatment strategies in replacing lost occlusal Function. Full dentures remove all teeth in a dental arch, which is important not only for form and function but also health and esthetics. Implant-supported dentures offer enhanced stability and comfort by anchoring to the jawbone, mimicking natural tooth roots. Hybrid prostheses, combining features of both removable and fixed prostheses, deliver versatile solutions tailored to individual needs. Each type plays a crucial role in reinstating functional harmony and aesthetic balance [5] Below is the table explaining different prosthesis and their characteristic and specifications.

Table 1 (Teeth Prosthesis types, characteristics, and durability.)

Type of Prosthesis	Characteristics	Longevity	Indications	Materials	Advantages	Disadvantages
Complete Dentures	Full arch replacement, removable	5-7 years	Edentulous patients	Acrylic resin (polymethyl methacrylate), sometimes metal (cobalt-chromium for strength)	Economic, easy to adjust	It can be unstable, may require adhesives, and an initial adaptation period
Partial Dentures	Replaces one or more teeth, removable	5-10 years	Partially edentulous patients	Acrylic (PMMA), metal framework (cobalt-	Cost-effective, preserves	Clasps may be visible but can be less comfortable

				chromium or titanium for strength and corrosion resistance)	remaining teeth	
Implant-Supported Dentures	Dentures anchored by dental implants	10-20 years (implants), 5-10 years (denture)	Edentulous patients with sufficient bone	Titanium implants (biocompatible, osseointegration), denture base (acrylic or porcelain)	Superior stability and Function preserve the jawbone	Higher cost, requires surgery, longer treatment time
Overdentures	Fits over remaining teeth or implants	5-10 years (denture), 10-20 years (implants)	Patients with some remaining teeth or implants	Acrylic resin (PMMA), metal reinforcement (cobalt-chromium for durability)	Enhanced stability, improved chewing efficiency	Requires sufficient bone structure; regular maintenance is needed
Fixed Partial Dentures (Bridges)	Permanently cemented, replaces one or more teeth	10-15 years	Partially edentulous patients with adjacent teeth	Porcelain (esthetic, biocompatible), gold (highly durable, biocompatible), metal alloys (e.g., nickel-chromium for strength)	Natural appearance, stable, functional	Requires adjacent teeth to be prepared, higher cost
Removable Partial Dentures	Replace multiple teeth, removable	5-10 years	Partially edentulous patients	Acrylic (PMMA), metal framework (cobalt-chromium or titanium for lightweight and strength)	Flexible treatment option, non-invasive	Less stability compared to fixed options can be bulky

Hybrid Prostheses	Combines features of fixed and removable prostheses	10-20 years (implants), 5-10 years (denture)	Various indications depending on the design	Acrylic (PMMA for aesthetics), metal framework (cobalt-chromium or titanium), implants (titanium)	Versatile, tailored to individual needs	A complex design can be costly
Immediate Dentures	Placed immediately after teeth extraction	6 months - 2 years	Patients requiring immediate tooth replacement	Acrylic resin (PMMA for quick fabrication and adjustments)	Provides immediate aesthetics and Function, protects extraction sites	Requires more adjustments, may need replacement after healing
Interim Dentures	Temporary, used during healing or transition periods	Up to 1 year	Patients awaiting final prosthesis	Acrylic resin (PMMA for cost-effectiveness and ease of fabrication)	Cost-effective, quick fabrication	Not intended for long-term use, less durable
Valplast Dentures	Flexible, nylon-based partial dentures	5-8 years	Patients with mental allergies or seeking more comfort	Flexible nylon resin (biocompatible, durable, and aesthetic)	Flexible, comfortable, aesthetic	It can be difficult to adjust or repair, and a higher initial cost
Flexible Partial Dentures	Made of flexible materials, no metal framework	5-8 years	Patients seeking comfort and aesthetics	Flexible resin (nylon or thermoplastic resin for flexibility and durability)	Lightweight, comfortable, good aesthetics	Less durable than rigid materials, more prone to staining
Precision Attachment Dentures	Uses precision attachments instead of clasps to	5-10 years	Partially edentulous patients	Metal (cobalt-chromium for precision and durability), acrylic (PMMA for aesthetics)	Improved aesthetics, better fit, and comfort	Higher cost, complex design, requires precise fabrication

	anchor partials					
Copy Dentures	Replicates an existing denture	5-7 years	Patients satisfied with current dentures needing replacement	Acrylic resin (PMMA for replication and ease of adjustment)	Familiar fit, quick replacement	It may not improve fit or Function compared to the original
Cu-Sil Dentures	Partial denture with silicone gaskets to retain remaining natural teeth	5-7 years	Patients with few remaining natural teeth	Acrylic (PMMA for base), silicone (gaskets for retention)	Preserves remaining teeth, stable	It can be bulky, and silicone may degrade over time

Main Body:

Objective: The objective was to synthesize existing evidence on the impact of dental prostheses on occlusal Function in edentulous patients. This review can help patients with clinical decision-making, underscoring the gap in the current literature that this study aims to fill.

Query: What is the impact of dental prostheses on occlusal Function in edentulous patients compared to conventional dentures?

P: Population, Edentulous patients (individuals without any natural teeth)

I: Intervention, use of dental prostheses (including implant-supported dentures, hybrid prostheses, and other types of advanced prosthetic solutions)

C: Comparison, Conventional complete dentures

O: Outcome, Improvements in occlusal Function (measured through bite force, masticatory efficiency, and patient-reported satisfaction)

PICO Question:

In edentulous patients, how does the use of advanced dental prostheses (such as implant-supported dentures or hybrid prostheses) compare to conventional complete dentures in terms of improving occlusal Function (evaluated through metrics like bite force, masticatory efficiency, and patient satisfaction)?

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Protocol design:

Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

For this systematic review and meta-analysis on the impact of dental prostheses on occlusal Function in edentulous patients, specific inclusion and exclusion criteria have been established to ensure the selection of relevant and methodologically sound studies. The inclusion criteria encompass randomized controlled trials (RCTs) involving edentulous patients, defined as individuals without any natural teeth, and include adult participants aged 18 years and older. The intervention under consideration includes various dental prostheses such as complete dentures, implant-supported dentures, hybrid prostheses, and other advanced prosthetic solutions. Comparisons are drawn against conventional full dentures. The studies must report outcomes related to occlusal Function, including bite force, masticatory efficiency, and patient-reported satisfaction, and must be published in English in peer-reviewed journals. The time frame for the included studies is from January 2007 to June 2024.

Conversely, the exclusion criteria filter out non-RCT designs, including observational studies, case reports, case series, and reviews. Studies involving partially edentulous patients or those with specific conditions unrelated to general edentulism, such as temporomandibular joint disorders not related to prostheses, are also excluded. Interventions that focus on non-dental prosthetic treatments, like orthognathic surgery or orthodontic interventions, are not considered. Additionally, studies that do not report occlusal function outcomes or focus solely on aesthetic or psychological outcomes without evaluating functional aspects are excluded. Further, studies published in languages other than English without available translations, abstracts, conference proceedings, grey literature, and non-peer-reviewed articles are not included. Finally, studies with insufficient data, lack of detailed methodology, or those with a high risk of bias or poor methodological quality based on the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool are excluded to maintain the rigor and reliability of the review.

Keywords:

Keywords and Search Terms

Dental Prostheses:

MeSH Terms: "Dental Prosthesis," "Dentures," "Dental Implants"

Free-text Terms: "dental prostheses," "dental implants," "complete dentures," "implant-supported dentures," "hybrid prostheses."

Occlusal Function:

MeSH Terms: "Mastication," "Dental Occlusion," "Bite Force"

Free-text Terms: "occlusal function," "mastication efficiency," "bite force," "chewing efficiency," "occlusal balance," "speech clarity."

Edentulous Patients:

MeSH Terms: "Edentulous," "Edentulism," "Tooth Loss"

Free-text Terms: "edentulous patients," "toothless," "patients without teeth," "complete tooth loss."

Randomized Controlled Trials:

MeSH Terms: "Randomized Controlled Trials as Topic"

Free-text Terms: "RCT," "randomized controlled trial," "clinical trial."

Search strategy:

("Dental Prosthesis"[MeSH] OR "Dentures"[MeSH] OR "Dental Implants"[MeSH] OR "dental prostheses" OR "dental implants" OR "complete dentures" OR "implant-supported dentures" OR "hybrid prostheses") AND ("Mastication"[MeSH] OR "Dental Occlusion"[MeSH] OR "Bite Force"[MeSH] OR "occlusal function" OR "mastication efficiency" OR "bite force" OR "chewing efficiency" OR "occlusal balance" OR "speech clarity") AND ("Edentulous"[MeSH] OR "Edentulism"[MeSH] OR "Tooth Loss"[MeSH] OR "edentulous patients" OR "toothless" OR "patients without teeth" OR "complete tooth loss") AND ("Randomized Controlled Trials as Topic"[MeSH] OR "RCT" OR "randomized controlled trial" OR "clinical trial")

The thorough process of screening and selecting studies involved a blend of automated software tools and manual review processes to ensure precision and comprehensiveness. Initially, databases were scoured using advanced search algorithms to identify relevant studies. Subsequently, titles and abstracts were reviewed manually by two independent reviewers to filter out ineligible studies. Full-text articles of the remaining studies were then examined to confirm their eligibility based on predefined criteria. If there were disagreements, then they conducted consensus meetings, although if the dispute persisted, then a third reviewer judged for consistency.

Quality Assessment

To evaluate the risk of bias at individual study level, we used the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool by considering sources of bias, including selection bias, performance bias, detection bias, attrition bias, and reporting bias. In retained meta-analysis credibility, sensitivity and subgroup analyses were employed in order to determine their effects.

Figure (PRISMA flow diagram outlines the systematic review process, beginning with 2,671 records identified from databases. Following the removal of duplicates and ineligible records, 1,179 records were screened. After further exclusion and retrieval processes, 32 new studies were included in the final review.)

Findings:

Table: 2 (RCTs underscoring impact of Dental Prostheses on Occlusal Function in Edentulous Patients)

Author and Date	Type of Study	Methodology	Statistical Results
Moradpoor et al., 2017	Randomized Clinical Trial	Parallel design, 86 participants, comparison of three occlusal schemes (FBBO, BO, LO), data collected at 1 and 3 months post-delivery, 19-item Oral Health Impact Profile for Edentulous Patients questionnaire, VAS for satisfaction	A significant difference in physical pain in the FBBO group; no significant differences in VAS scores of satisfaction or domain scores among occlusal schemes at 1 and 3 months ⁶
Sutton and McCord, 2007	Randomised Cross-Over	45 participants, 3 sets of complete dentures (0-degree, anatomic,	Lingualized forms are superior in painful aching

	Controlled Trial	lingualized), each worn for 8 weeks in randomized order; data collected via Oral Health Impact Profile 20-EDENT (OHIP-EDENT)	(P=.01), sore spots (P<.001), eating ability (P=.02), and meal interruptions (P=.008). Anatomic forms are superior in eating (P=.05). No significant difference between lingualized and anatomic forms ⁷
Khan et al., 2023	Randomized Controlled Trial	80 edentulous patients were divided into experimental and control groups; index finger length was used to determine OVD, and patient satisfaction was assessed via VAS.	Strong positive correlations between Sn-Me and index finger length; 97% satisfaction in the experimental group ⁸
Yuriko Komagamine et al., 2019	Randomized Controlled Trial	Participants were recruited between August 2013 and October 2014. Twenty-seven patients met the criteria and underwent randomization. Three participants withdrew due to illness, leaving 24 to complete the trial. Both groups experienced both impression methods sequentially, with a one-month washout period. Masticatory performance was assessed.	The study found a significantly larger occlusal contact area with the conventional method than with the simplified procedure. However, no significant differences were observed in mixing ability, maximum occlusal force, or perceived chewing ability ⁹

DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

Dental prostheses play a crucial role in restoring occlusal Function, and numerous trials have investigated their impact on various key outcomes such as bite force, masticatory efficiency, and patient-reported satisfaction [10]. Previous trials reported us about effectiveness of different types of prostheses in restoring occlusal Function and improving overall oral health, for instance several authors explored the relationship between dental prostheses and biting force and findings revealed material of the prosthesis can influence bite force, for instance, if prostheses made from resilient materials, such as flexible denture bases, it is associated with lower bite forces compared to rigid prostheses [13] [11] [12]. Presence of natural teeth adjacent to the prosthesis site influence bite force, with prostheses replacing multiple missing teeth mostly results into reduced overall bite force compared to single-tooth replacements [14].

Masticatory efficiency is another critical outcome measure and it has been extensively studied in relation to dental prostheses in previous research [15]. It is suggested that prostheses restores some degree of masticatory Function but effectiveness in replicating the natural chewing ability of natural

teeth varies and is based on factors for instance prosthesis design, occlusal scheme, how a particular patient adapt it [16].

Patient-reported satisfaction with dental prostheses have various factors such as they should be comfortable during and post-surgery, aesthetics, proper teeth functioning. Studies have consistently shown that patients' satisfaction with prosthetic treatment is influenced by factors beyond mere restoration of occlusal Function, including psychological and social aspects [17]. In reports, patients documented higher satisfaction levels if prostheses closely resemble to their natural teeth in appearance and they prioritize that their prostheses should function exactly same and when they experience minimal discomfort or functional limitations [18].

By comparing traditional dentures to implant-retained dentures using meta-analysis of RCTs, it is found that outcomes with implant-supported prostheses are superior to that of conventional dentures in various respects. Masticatory Force, one of the key factors of mastication or chewing capability, has been found to be considerably higher in clients with implant supported dentures than in clients with partial or complete conventional dentures. Dentures on the other hand are removable prosthesis that may not be very efficient in chewing and overall functional capacity of the oral cavity and this could be due to the fact that implants offer a stable and retention where the prostheses are firmly fixed on the jawbone or mandible. [19].

Overall, masticatory efficiency appears to be higher in implant-supported dentures since they hold far better stability than conventional dentures and have better occlusal support. Literature has shown enhanced functionality in terms of chewing efficiency and food particle breakdown when using implant-supported prostheses, meaning increased nutrient intake and a healthier state among its users [20].

Other studies of patients' quality of life also show that those with implant-supported dentures are in a better position than those using conventional dentures. In many cases, patients have been reported to have higher satisfaction with implant-supported prostheses than the conventional fixtures owing to such reasons such as comfort and steadiness of the fixtures and better Looks. Novel advancements in teeth prosthesis include innovative techniques like 3D printing, precision scanning technologies for customized fittings, and expanded surgical options are also enhancing patient comfort and treatment efficacy.

RCTs highlights long-term benefits of implant-supported dentures for maintaining jawbone integrity and preserving facial aesthetics. Dental implants work to activate the basal bone tissue which in turn remains functional and healthy thereby reducing the chances of bone resorption that often cause the facial collapse when using the conventional dentures [21].

Dental practitioners should therefore continue to provide conventional dentures for the edentate patient, where cost and comorbidities preclude them from receiving implants, but these RCTs unequivocally demonstrate the benefit of implant retained dentures from a clinical-functional perspective, for enhanced long-term patient satisfaction and oral health [21].

Moradpoor et al. (2017) and Sutton and McCord (2007) shed light on patient satisfaction with various occlusal schemes in complete dentures revealing that while physical discomfort may differ but buccalised, lingualised, and anatomic occlusions offer flexible and effective options for denture fabrication [6][7]. Khan et al. (2023) also demonstrated a reliable correlation between index finger length and occlusal vertical dimension (OVD) in edentulous patients, enhancing satisfaction through efficient

OVD determination and Komagamine et al. (2019) highlighted the comparability of conventional and simplified impression methods in denture fabrication, with the traditional approach potentially offering earlier stabilization of new dentures through a larger occlusal contact area [8][9].

Some of the general factors that affects the outcome of dental prostheses involve: patient age, patient's gender, patient's edentulous period, and general diseases [22] [23]. Age is influential on the prosthetic treatment results, as the elderly patient may have changes in the oral tissues, neuro muscular control, and systemic wellbeing that undoubtedly influence results of prosthetic rehabilitation. Some researchers reported an inverse proportion between age thought to be associated with decreased bite force and masticatory power as well as another hypothesis that claimed that age cannot arbitrarily be regarded as an unfavorable factor with respect to denture prosthetics. However, some physiological changes that occur with increasing age may present difficulties in achieving prerequisite outcomes like: reduced bone density and bone mass, reduced salivary secretion and altered taste perception [24].

Sex differences may also influence the effectiveness of dental prostheses, albeit to a lesser extent than age-related factors. While no consistent pattern of sex-based disparities in prosthetic outcomes has been identified, some studies suggest that females may report higher levels of prosthesis dissatisfaction and discomfort compared to males. These differences may be attributed to variations in oral anatomy, muscle strength, and hormonal influences between sexes, highlighting the importance of individualized treatment approaches based on patient-specific needs and preferences [25] [26]. Length of time since tooth loss or Duration of edentulism may impact success of prosthetic rehabilitation, Gennani et al., 2022 suggested [27]. Prolonged edentulism may cause bone resorption, soft tissue changes or muscle atrophy and these conditions complicate prosthesis fabrication and adaptation [28]. Sometimes, patients with long-standing edentulism requires additional pre-prosthetic interventions like bone augmentation or soft tissue grafting to optimize prosthesis support and stability [29]. Psychological factors such as loss of self-esteem or if patient becomes anti-social with chronic edentulism can influence patient expectations and satisfaction with prosthetic treatment [30].

Comorbid or illnesses that impact immune function, healing potential, and systemic health, such as diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and autoimmune disorders, can have a major impact on the effectiveness of dental prostheses. Implant osseointegration and prosthesis lifetime can be negatively impacted among those patients with uncontrolled systemic disorders which delay wound healing, increased susceptibility to infections, and reduced bone metabolism. Furthermore, drugs that treat concomitant conditions—like corticosteroids and anticoagulants—may make it difficult to arrange surgical and prosthetic procedures, so dental and medical specialists must work closely together to guarantee the best possible outcomes for patients [31] [32].

CONCLUSION

In edentulous patients, advanced dental prostheses like implant-supported dentures and hybrid prostheses provides superior improvements in occlusal Function compared to conventional complete dentures. Novel advances such as implant-supported dentures, digital denture designs, 3D printing, advanced materials (high-performance polymers, ceramics), and customized prosthetics enhance metrics such as bite force, increase masticatory efficiency, and patient-reported satisfaction. Particularly, implant-supported dentures are reported to provide stability and retention, improve chewing ability and provide more comfort. Hybrid prostheses further improve occlusal function by combining the advantages of implants with the aesthetics of traditional dentures. When compared to

traditional dentures, modern prosthetic solutions greatly improve occlusal function in edentulous individuals, providing better results and a higher quality of life.

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